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Innovative Climate-Control System to Extend Range of Electric Vehicles and Improve Comfort (XERIC)

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RIA n° 653605

Start Date: 1st June 2015 - Duration: 36 months

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Report:

XERIC’s 3rd Newsletter

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Summary:

This is the third of XERIC’s e-newsletters. The e-newsletters are released twice a year. This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created and sent and who the subscribers are.

The newsletter is then displayed.

The appendices display the documents that open when one clicks on the links in the online version of the newsletter.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
05.12.2016	Guyène SOULA (EMH)	Preparation version 1 (V1)	

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1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to the *WordPress* Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically **as emails**. The software splits the mailing list in several sub-lists so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Subscribers

Mailing lists were created in 2015 for the different communication purposes that we may have for the XERIC project. The starting point was each of the XERIC partners and their own professional mailing lists. There were 123 subscribers in 2015. In May 2016, the total number of subscribers rose to 150.

Right now (December 2016), the total number of subscribers is 269.

The bulk of the new subscribers is made of the following:

- 30 other EU-funding projects working on the theme of electric vehicles;
- an additional 64 email addresses collected *via* the registration form to XERIC's 1st public workshop (these 64 persons answered yes to being kept informed about future events).

XERIC's third newsletter was sent to all 269 subscribers.

People can unsubscribe thanks to an "unsubscribe" button at the bottom of the e-newsletter.

3. Newsletter 3

Please click on the following link to read XERIC's 3rd newsletter:

http://xeric.eu/?wysija-page=1&controller=email&action=view&email_id=35&wysijap=subscriptions&user_id=3

Screenprints of the newsletters are displayed on the next pages.

See appendices for all the links to pdf documents that can be opened when browsing the newsletter online.

Newsletter 3 - December 2016

Editorial by Project Coordinator

We're half-way through XERIC's journey: we have just concluded the third semester of activities of a very challenging scientific and technological adventure related to electric vehicles. XERIC has taken up the challenge of extending the range of electric vehicles by developing a **novel climate control system**. The climate control system adds an original desiccant cycle

to a traditional vapour compression cycle. (...)

XERIC is **keen on promoting synergy** by **clustering with other EC-funded projects**: (...) the first joint public event took place in November 2016 in Bologna, Italy. One hundred participants from all over Europe got together (...) and grew their network. (...)

And **Save The Date**: a new get-together is already in sight: April 2017, Monaco.

Nino Gaeta - GVS spa - XERIC's Coordinator

[Read full editorial](#)

Get to know the XERIC researchers - INTERVIEWS

Bernardo CERRAI

Frigomar Srl, Italy

Bernardo is into R&D for new high efficiency air conditioners and special systems for cooling applications: he's a lab and technical office person!

"What is exciting in XERIC is to design, develop and operate a new refrigeration cycle that has been studied from a theoretical point of view and that is completely

different from the ones available today [on the market]."

[Read the full interview](#)

Dr. Federica BOERO

TICASS, Italy

Federica Boero has a PhD in materials science. Her thesis dealt with "The study of kesterites as materials for photovoltaic devices". At TICASS, Federica is doing something else entirely. She is in charge of the laboratory tests for XERIC and says she is supported by a very nice team of experts!

[Read the full interview](#)

Discover XERIC partners' expertise

FRIGOMAR Srl

Frigomar Srl is a company designing and manufacturing heating, ventilation, air-conditioning and refrigeration systems for marine/industrial applications. Frigomar manufactures chillers, fan coils, self-contained units, custom-made fridges and freezers and cold rooms suitable for yachts and working boats as well as specific industrial applications (offshore cold water systems). Over the past five years, the company has been developing new products representing a great

innovation in the marine market, such as the very first introduction of R410A refrigerant fluid for an improved energy efficiency.

[Read more](#)

SAVE THE DATE: *New Progress in air conditioning systems for EVs*

Sessions devoted to "**New progress in air conditioning systems for electric vehicles**" are getting organised by the XERIC, JOSPEL and OPTEMUS European-funded projects. They should be part of the [EVER Conference](#) to be held in **April 2017** (11th to 13th) in Monaco.

Keep a keen eye on your email inbox: you will receive more information in January 2017.

100 participants at *Improving Energy Efficiency in EVs* event

One hundred participants from all over Europe got together to learn what the European Commission is doing for electric mobility, get a unique insight into the latest research and development on energy management in electric vehicles and establish new contacts for collaborations thanks to bilateral meetings.

[View the speakers' presentations.](#)

[View pictures of the event.](#)

www.xeric.eu

[Unsubscribe](#)

4. Appendices

- Editorial by Nino Gaeta, XERIC's coordinator;
- 2 interviews (Bernardo Cerrai – Frigomar ; Federica Boero – TICASS);
- Slides displaying pictures of XERIC's 1st workshop (one-day event devoted to Electric Vehicles – November 2016 - Bologna, Italy).

XERIC's European adventure well on its track!

Welcome to the third XERIC newsletter.

We're half-way through XERIC's journey: we have just concluded the third semester of activities of a very challenging scientific and technological adventure related to electric vehicles. XERIC has taken up the challenge of extending the range of electric vehicles by developing a **novel climate control system**.

The climate control system adds an original desiccant cycle to a traditional vapour compression cycle (VCC). In detail, the desiccant cycle is based on an innovative component, specifically designed within the XERIC project and called **three-fluids combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC)**, that simultaneously works with air, desiccant solution and refrigerant. One important part of the 3F-CMC is the **semi-permeable membrane** that lets water vapour to pass through (thus dehumidifying the air) while preventing the liquid water (the desiccant is indeed an aqueous solution) to go in the reverse direction. Our aim is to develop a **Polyvinildene fluoride membrane by using ecofriendly manufacturing technologies** and upgrade its already high hydrophobicity by a treatment based on indirect plasma. The novel climate control system will be completed by the use of **an innovative electronic control system**, which we are also developing. Moreover, the VCC can operate also as a heat pump through a 4-way valve, allowing for both cooling and heating of air.

XERIC is keen on promoting synergy by **clustering** with other EC-funded projects: the JOSPEL and OPTEMUS European projects contributed to a one-day workshop devoted to improving energy efficiency in electric vehicles. This first joint public event took place on November 24, 2016 in Bologna, Italy. More than **100 participants** from all over Europe got a unique insight into the latest research and development on energy management in electric vehicles and grew their network.

More on page 2

Save the date:

A new get-together is already in sight. XERIC, OPTEMUS and JOSPEL will organize a second workshop in the framework of EVER2017, a Conference that will take place in Monaco, FR on April 11-13, 2017.

In this edition of our newsletter, you'll also get a **glimpse into the daily working life** of Bernardo Cerrai from Frigomar and Federica Boero from TICASS, two of the researcher involved in XERIC.

On behalf of the XERIC partners, I am glad to report that we are strongly committed to **creating new intellectual and material know-how** for the reduction of energy consumption for heating, ventilation and air conditioning in electric cars, and in general in air-conditioned environments.

We welcome any comments or suggestion from all people interested in our project and we invite you to read more about it on our website: www.xeric.eu.

We hope you enjoy this issue.

Nino Gaeta
GVS SPA
XERIC's Coordinator

European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Bernardo CERRAI**

Technical Manager at Frigomar Srl

Italy

I am from Lerici, a wonderful bay of the Ligurian Riviera named the town of poets. I graduated in mechanical engineering in 1995 at Genoa University. In the following years I worked in Italy and France for different companies (Olimpia Splendid, Brandt, Electrolux) dealing mainly with the research and development of household appliances such as air conditioners, washing machines. I joined Frigomar in 2004 specializing in marine refrigeration and air conditioning. ■■■

■■■ At Frigomar I have been mainly working at the research and development of new high efficiency air conditioners and special systems for cooling applications.

What does your daily job look like?

I work very closely with the research and development team therefore I spend most of my time at the labs and technical office. Sometimes I find myself abroad to meet suppliers and customers.

What objectives do you have to reach to contribute to the XERIC project? How challenging is it?

We have first to develop a very efficient air conditioning control system, then to design and manufacture a new air conditioning system composed by a traditional compressor vapor cycle coupled with a desiccant loop. The project is very challenging since the proposed technology is completely new and it requires studies and experiments on the system never carried out so far.

What excites you in XERIC?

To design, develop and operate a new refrigeration cycle that has been studied from a theoretical point of view and that is completely different from the ones available today and based on the existing technology.

From your perspective, what is innovative with XERIC?

The possibility to considerably increase the energy efficiency of the system by dehumidifying the air through desiccant membranes, so to reduce the compression ratio. If the experiments confirm the theoretical analysis, a great innovation in the air conditioning field will be achieved.

What are the major challenges to be overcome in XERIC, according to you?

All the XERIC activities are very intensive since theoretical, phenomenological and applied research are involved. In detail the challenges to overcome are mainly the manufacturing of the 3F-CMC vapor exchanger which controls the desiccant cycle, as well as the new refrigeration cycle that must ensure the correct XERIC operation.

Thanks for answering my questions Bernardo and all the best for XERIC!

Frigomar, a partner in the XERIC project

Frigomar Srl is a company designing and manufacturing heating, ventilation, air-conditioning and refrigeration systems for marine/industrial applications. Frigomar manufactures chillers, fan coils, self-contained units, custom made fridges and freezers and cold rooms suitable for yachts and working boats as well as particular industrial applications (offshore cold water systems).

Over the past 5 years the company has been developing new products representing a great innovation in the marine market, from the very first introduction of R410A refrigerant fluid allowing a better energy efficiency, to the last inverter Brushless DC technology with great advantages in term of energy saving, quality and comfort of the inside environment.

The variable speed chiller 607NT Frigomar was nominated at DAME Amsterdam METS 2013 as an innovative product.

www.frigomar.com/en/

XERIC in brief

XERIC is a European Research & Innovation Project

Start date:

1st June 2015

End date:

31st May 2018

Number of partners: 8

Coordinator:

Dr. Eng. S. GAETA

GVS spa

Italy

Programme:

H2020-GV-2014

Project Reference: 653605

European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Federica BOERO**

Researcher at TICASS, Italy

.../... I then proceeded with my studies with a PhD in materials science. I presented my thesis with the title "The study of kesterites as materials for photovoltaic devices" at the end of February 2016. And I started my work in TICASS as young researcher the 1st of April 2016, in a totally different field from my studies. My work is principally focused on the laboratory tests for XERIC and for other smaller projects.

What objectives do you have to reach to contribute to the XERIC project? How challenging is it?

I started my work in XERIC project at the beginning of April. I am the responsible of the laboratory tests, but I am supported by a very nice team of experts (Professors Capannelli, Nannei, Isetti and Claudia Cattaneo), who are helping me with everything related to the project!

What excites you in the XERIC project?

The XERIC project gives me the opportunity to work in team with experts, and to learn a lot of new things. Furthermore, I really like that XERIC is a "green" project!

Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself?

I studied Chemistry at the University of Genoa, the city where I was born and where I live. During my master degree I investigated the phase diagram of a ternary alloy, in collaboration with the University of Vienna, where I stayed 6 months within the Erasmus programme .../...

Date of interview: November 2016
Publication: December 2016 - 1/2

From your perspective, what is innovative with XERIC?

XERIC is an innovative project because it introduces a new concept in the climate control systems.

On a more general note, what is appealing to you in being a researcher?

In my opinion, a researcher has the possibility to use his/her brain for trying to change something.

**Thanks for answering my questions
Federica and all the best for XERIC!**

What is TICASS?

TICASS S.c.r.l stands for Tecnologie innovative per il Controllo Ambientale e lo Sviluppo Sostenibile, i.e, TICASS deals with Innovative Technologies for Environmental Control and Sustainable Development. It is a non-profit Consortium based in Italy, in the Liguria region.

TICASS was created in March 2010 by universities, research organizations, small, medium and large companies to promote, disseminate, transfer and enhance activities of research and technology transfer in the field of energy and environment, with a particular focus on sustainable development and quality of life.

Role of TICASS in XERIC

TICASS is carrying work to design and model the three-fluids-combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC) and XERIC's climate control system. The University of Genoa (UNIGE) co-invented and patented the 3F-CMC. The current development within XERIC's framework is supported by these patents.

www.ticass.it

XERIC in brief

XERIC is a European Research & Innovation Project

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www.xeric.eu

IMPROVING *Energy Efficiency* IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES

November 24th, 2016
Bologna, Italy

IMPROVING
Energy Efficiency
IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES

Big flag to welcome participants at the venue's main entrance.

Reception desk: full colours of the Electric Vehicles Day are featured

IMPROVING *Energy Efficiency* IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES

PARTICIPANTS

Austria	1
Belgium	1
Bosnia-Herzegovina	1
Denmark	3
France	6
Germany	8
Italy	58
Luxembourg	2
Portugal	2
Spain	14
United Kingdom	4
Total	100

One hundred participants got together for an intense one-day event made up of a great mix of talks with top-notch speakers and bilateral meetings.

IMPROVING Energy Efficiency IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES

24 November 2016 - Bologna, Italy

INSIGHTS
INTO H2020 INITIATIVES
ON ENERGY MANAGEMENT

AGENDA

MORNING		
When	What	Who
08:45	<i>Welcome coffee and registration</i>	
09:15	Welcome	Lamberto SALVAN - JOSPEL Head of Business Development Alke - Italy
09:20	XERIC project: Hybrid climate control system able to control separately temperature and humidity	Stefano LAZZARI - XERIC Professor of Technical Physics and HVAC systems Department of Architectural Sciences University of Genoa - Italy <i>XERIC's Deputy Coordinator</i>
09:35	JOSPEL project –Optimisation of interior temperature control management	Begoña GALINDO GALIANA - JOSPEL Senior Polymer Research Aimplas - Spain
09:50	OPTEMUS project: Leveraging low energy consumption and energy harvesting.	Alois STEINER - OPTEMUS Co-Team Leader for Thermal Management & Mobile Air Conditioning Virtual Vehicle Research Center in Graz Austria <i>OPTEMUS's Coordinator</i>
10:05	On the importance of Clustering - Towards tangible benefits for Europe within the framework of INEA	Gilbert RIOS – XERIC Professor Emeritus - Chemical Engineering French National School for Engineering European Membrane House CEO
10:15	Financing Electric Mobility thanks to H2020 INEA - Innovation and Networks Executive Agency	David GUEDJ Senior Project Manager INEA European Commission
10:35	From Cell to System – A brief introduction to the design of a battery system	Maximilian BRUCH - JOSPEL Project Manager Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE - Germany
10:55	<i>Coffee break</i>	

11:15	Preconditioning and Human Machine Interface	Andrés CALDEVILLA - OPTEMUS Advanced Research Technical Manager Denso - Germany
11:35	Low energy heating system based on Joule effect	Begoña GALINDO GALIANA - JOSPEL Senior Polymer Researcher Aimplas - Spain
11:50	Thermoelectrics and Joule effect for a low energy thermal management (heating and cooling)	Silvia ORTEGA – JOSPEL PhD student (industrial PhD programme) CIDETE Ingenieros S.L - Spain
12:05	How to create a micro-climate around the passengers to dispense with climatizing the entire cabin	Felix WEIDMANN - OPTEMUS Project Engineer Fraunhofer LBF Division Plastics in Darmstadt - Germany
12:25	<i>Lunch break + DEMOS and posters</i>	

AFTERNOON		
When	What	Who
14:00	The electric vehicle value chain inside the Emilia Romagna Smart Specialization Strategy: a theme for European Industrial Modernization Platform?	Francesco Paolo AUSIELLO Strategic Projects Manager ASTER - High Tech Network - Italy <i>XERIC's Strategic Advisory Board</i>
14:20	Polymer-based multicomponent water-vapor selective membranes and other examples of recent membrane developments at KAUST	Klaus-Viktor PEINEMANN Professor in Chemical and Biological Engineering King Abdullah University of Science and Technology - KAUST - Saudi Arabia <i>XERIC's Strategic Advisory Board</i>
14:40	Process Intensification for the Design for the Factory of Future (Towards a plant in a shoe box or in a banana container)	Jean-Claude CHARPENTIER Professor of Chemical Engineering Director Emeritus of Research Laboratoire Réactions et Génie des Procédés CNRS / ENSI - France <i>XERIC's Strategic Advisory Board</i>
15:00	Wrap up and presenting B2Bs	Lamberto SALVAN – JOSPEL Alke - Italy
15:10	<i>Visit – Gallery Tour</i> Museum of Machines by Dayanita Singh, Indian photographer	
15:45 to 18:00	Networking: B2B meetings	

WIFI: Select «Wifi MAST». No password needed.